

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS – VOL. 14 (2021)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2021,
vol. 14

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AFFECTING TEACHERS` WORK MOTIVATION IN LOWER SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ALBANIA

Enida Kume¹

Abstract

A sample of 198 Albanian teachers in lower secondary schools, randomly selected, was used for investigate the relationship between work motivation and their demographic factors. Descriptive statistics, analyze of variances (ANOVA) and logistic regression analyze were used to analyze the data. The overall finding was that: (i) between work motivation among the teachers in lower secondary schools in Albania and their demographic characteristics, a significant relationship was identified, (ii) no significant differences in the level of work motivation related to the gender of the teacher; (iii) the age and seniority of teachers are factors that affect the work motivation among teachers. Teachers aged > 40 years and teachers who have > 10 years of work experience are more motivated at work; (iv) the civil status of the teacher affects the work motivation but this result is a consequence of the statistical difference in the levels of motivation at work between married teachers and others, only; (v) the study does not support the hypothesis about the relationship between property status of the school, its location and the level of work motivation among the teachers.

Key words: *work motivation, demographic factors, teachers in lower secondary school*

Introduction

In their paper Urošević, S., Milijić. (2012) emphasize: "Many authors are interested in the problem of motivation because if understood, it results in: improving efficiency and creativity, improving the quality of working life in the organization, improving the competitive advantage

¹ Lectures, Department of Pedagogies, Faculty of Education, "Aleksandër Moisiu" University, Durrës, Albania.
Contact: enidak@hotmail.it

and the company's success." Meanwhile it is important to note that currently "no theory is good enough to envisage what will motivate each employee, because what motivates some does not necessarily motivate all others (Unčanin et al. 2006). The study aimed at identifying the factors that affect the work motivation among teachers is one of the areas of research that has attracted much attention of researchers. Utomo, H.B. (2018) declare that "The complex tasks and responsibilities of achieving educational goals relate to teachers' motivation, so that good intentions will encourage teacher activities. Teachers become educators based on their motivation to teach. If a teacher has no motivation then they are unlikely to be an effective educator". According to Jyoti & Sharma, (2009) this "made very important the need for teachers to have all the necessary conditions for them to be satisfied with their work and to be as motivated and engaged as possible".

Work motivation among teachers is the result of the action of intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Praver dhe Oga-Baldwin (2008) among the external motivating factors for educational employees are listed salary, working conditions, relationship with the principal, etc.. and in the group of internal motivating factors include independence in action, cooperation with colleagues, self-realization and institutional support. They emphasize that internal motivating factors are more active and important for teachers in the first years of their work, while external motivating factors, in particular financial rewards such as salary, pension and social security, are the most important motivating and more powerful influencers on work motivation and job satisfaction in educational workers who have more seniority in education. Referring to the complexity of the factors and the mode of their action in work motivation among teachers, Börü, N. (2018) emphasizes that "it is necessary in any case to make an in-depth analysis of the mode of action of internal and external factors".

Various authors claim that demographic factors, such as teacher's gender, age, seniority, level of qualification, civil status, as well as socio-economic factors such as ownership of the school and its location, in the urban or rural area, affect on work motivation among teachers (Khan W.A. 2001, Mustafa M. Nur, Othman, N., 2010; Urošević, S., Milijić. 2012; Can.,S. 2015; Mark, A. 2015; Jiying Han, Hongbiao Yin., 2016; Kumar, A. 2017; Ates, H. K., Yilmaz, P. 2018; [Irnidayanti](#), Y., et al. 2020).

In Albania, there are very few studies focusing on evaluating the effect of demographic factors on work motivation among teachers in elementary and secondary schools.

The purpose of the present study was identification and evaluation of the relationship between demographic factors like as gender, age, seniority, civil status as well as socio-economic factors such as ownership of the school and its location, in the urban or rural area and work motivation among teachers in lower secondary school in Albania.

Objective

Identification and estimation the relationship between demographic and socio-economic factors with work motivation among teachers in lower secondary schools

Research questions

Are there differences in the level of work motivation among male and female teachers in lower secondary school?

Is the level of work motivation among teachers in lower secondary school affected by age, civil status and seniority?

Is there a difference in work motivation among teachers in and private lower secondary school teachers?

Is there a difference in work motivation among teachers working in lower secondary schools in urban and rural areas?

Data

The data for this study derived by the answers received from 198 teachers, in lower secondary schools distributed in the central region of Albania, where about 69% of the entire population lives. The questionnaire used to be compiled after consulting with data literature Bezati, F. (2012); Zhilla, E. (2014); Kotherrja, O. (2015); Teneqexhi, M. (2016); Tirana, J. (2018). The questionnaire consists of two parts:

(i) personal/demographic information (gender, age, civil status, seniority) and

(ii) teacher motivation scale: intrinsic motivation (14 questions) and extrinsic motivation (9 questions). The answers to the questions are the values of the Likert variables, with 5 scales: 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-between agreeing and disagree, 4-agree, 5-strongly agree. Consequently, the minimum score that can be obtained from the scale is 23, and the maximum score is 115. Accordingly, the scores between 23-54 were interpreted as the low level of motivation, scores between 55-84 were interpreted as the medium level of motivation, and scores between 85-115 were interpreted as the high level of motivation.

The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was found to be 0.79.

Features of the sample

Demographic features of the sample show in Table 1.

Table 1 Demographic features of the sample

Feature	Number	%
Gender		
Femal	162	81.8
Mal	36	18.2
Age		
20-30 years old	49	24.7
31-40 years old	80	40.4
>40 years old	69	34.8
Seniority		
< 5 years	55	27.8
5-10 years	67	33.8
>10 years	76	38.4
Civil status		
Celibate	31	15.7
Married	126	63.6
Divorced	29	14.6
Widow	12	6.1
Ownership of the school		
Private school	25	12.6
Public school	173	87.4
School location		
Urban area	141	71.8
Periurban/rural area	57	28.8

About 18% of teachers interviewed are male. In Albania, male teachers in lower secondary schools make up about 12-16%. Grouping of teachers by age is approximately the same as in the country. Regarding the indicator of ownership over the school, public or private school, the sample structure does not differ from the structure at the national level (12.6% vs 10.2%, $p < 0.05$). The same is the level of representation of the sample regarding the distribution of schools in urban and peri-urban / rural areas, (sample: 71.8% / 28.8% vs country: 67.3% / 32.7%, $p < 0.05$).

Data analysis methods

Descriptive statistical analysis will be used to evaluate the level of work motivation of teachers in the lower secondary schools. ANOVA one way and logistic regression analyze will be used to identify and evaluate the relationship between demographic, socio-economic factors and work motivation among teachers in the lower secondary

schools. Based on the logistic regression analysis it was estimated *odds ratios* that the teachers is motivated, corresponding of different levels for each demographic factor, and socio-economics factors: property status of schools and residential area where the school is locate. The binary logistic regression model was used is follow:

$$Y_{ijn} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}X_{1ij} + \beta_{2j}X_{2ij} + \epsilon_{ijn}$$

where:

Y - dependent variable, whose value is one of two states:

Teacher is motivated to work (1), Teacher is not motivated to work (0).

X_{1ij} - independent variables- demographic characteristics of teachers: gender, age, sinority, civil status

X_{2ij} - independent variables: socio-economic factors-property status of schools and residential area where the school is located.

The values of the dependent variable, which reflects the work motivation of teachers, were calculated according to the rule:

Teachers for whom the average of total scores of work motivation is ≤ 54 scores, are classified in the group who are not motivated, y = 0

Teachers for whom the average of total scores of work motivation is ≥ 55 scores, are classified to the group who are motivated, y = 1.

Results and discussions

The average of the scores of the work motivation among teachers is 80.3 ± 0.73 (Table 2). These values show that the overall work motivation of teachers evaluate at medium level. Consequently, it can be stated that, in general, motivational factors do not have a large motivational impact on the work of teachers in lower secondary school in Albania. The average for effect of extrinsic motivating factors is evaluated with 75.9 ± 0.39 scores (medium level) and for intrinsic motivating factors 85.1±0.86 scores (hight level). As can be seen, intrinsic factors turn out to be factors with the greatest positive effect on teachers' work motivation. This result is similar with that communicated by Bezati, F. (2012). Based on it, it can be stated that teachers in the lower secondary schools perform their work as a mission, which fills them with positive psycho-spiritual feelings.

Table 2. Average of work motivation

	Number	Minimum score	Maximum score	Average	sd
Work motivation	198	24	115	80.3	0.73
-intrinsic motivation	198	24	115	85.1	0.86
-extrinsic motivation	198	24	115	75.9	0.69

The averages of teachers' work motivation, corresponding to different demographic factors, are given in Table 3

Table 3 Average of work motivation corresponding to different demographic factors¹

Feature	Number	Mean	Standard deviation
Gender			
Female	162	81.02 ^a	8.16
Male	36	80.15 ^a	6.74
Age			
20-30 years old	49	76.5 ^a	7.15
31-40 years old	80	82.3 ^b	9.32
>40 years old	69	83.8 ^b	8.21
Seniority			
< 5 years	55	79.1 ^a	8.15
5-10 years	67	81.5 ^a	7.95
>10 years	76	84.7 ^b	8.04
Civil status			
Celibate	31	79.2 ^a	8.22
Married	126	84.3 ^b	7.16
Divorced	29	77.9 ^a	8.51
Widow	12	78.6 ^a	9.04

¹Corresponding means for each of the demographic factors, marked with different letters have a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

The teachers scores of attitudes towards work motivational factors do not significantly vary based on gender ($p > .05$). Can, S. (2015); Kumar, A. (2017) have published the same result, while Mustafa M. Nur., Othman, N., (2012) have identified the gender of the teacher as a demographic factor that has a statistically significant effect on teacher work motivation.

Based on the results of analysis of variance, ANOVA one way, (Table no. 4, 5, 6) can be judged whether or not, different demographic factors affect the work motivation among the teachers. The data in Table 4 show that the level of work motivation among teachers varies depending on their age ($p < 0.01$). Young teachers (20-30 years old) have the lowest level of work motivation (work $p < 0.05$).

Table 4. ANOVA - Age-dependent work motivation scores of the teachers

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean squares	F	p
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Between-group	724.3	2	362.1	3.52	<0.01
Within-group	20062.0	195	102.8		
Total	20786.3	197			

Age: 1: 20-30 years old, 2:31-40 years old, 3:>40 years old

Increasing the age of teachers is associated with increasing the level of motivation at work. The highest value of this level reaches teachers in the age group > 40 years. This is a result that differs from that communicated by Can, S. (2015), according to which, younger teachers are more affected by factors motivating teachers.

Seniority is a demographic feature which affects the level of work motivation of teachers. (Table 5). Teachers who have >10 years of work experience as educators, are more motivated than their colleagues with fewer years of work experience ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5. ANOVA - Teachers' motivation scores in relation to their seniority status

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean squares	F	p
Between-group	692.8	2	346.4	3.36	<0.05
Within-group	20093.2	195	103.0		
Total	20786.3	197			

Seniority: 1: > 5 years, 2:5-10 years, 3:>10 years

Analysis of variance (Table 6) has identified a statistically significant impact of teachers' civil status on the level of motivation in their work. Meanwhile, referring to the data in Table 3, it turns out that this impact is the only consequence of the difference in the level of motivation of married teachers compared to others. Married teachers are more motivated to work than their peers with other civil status.

Table 6. ANOVA - Teachers' motivation scores in relation to their civil status

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean squares	F	p
Between-group	939.6	3	313.9	3.07	<0.05
Within-group	19846.7	194	102.3		
Total	20786.3	197			

Civil status: 1: celibate, 2: married, 3: divorced, 4: widow

Sampling data did not identify a significant difference in the level of work motivation between teachers working in public schools and teachers working in private schools (80.82 ± 7.19 vs 79.56 ± 8.07 ; $p > 0.05$). No significant difference was found between the level of work

motivation among teachers working in schools in urban areas and those working in peri-urban / rural areas. (80.51 ± 8.21 vs 80.05 ± 9.03 ; $p > 0.05$).

In Table 7 are shown the results of logistic regression

Table 7. Results of logistic regression

Demographic feature	Dependent variable: Work motivation Motivated (1), Not motivated (0)	
	β	odds ratios
Gender Reference: Mal		
Female	0.071 ^{NS}	1.074
Age Referenca: 20-30 years old		
31-40 years old	0.484 [†]	1.623
>40 years old	0.665 [†]	1.945
Seniority Reference: < 5 years		
5-10 years	0.217 ^{NS}	1.243
>10 years	1.048 [†]	2.852
Civil status Reference: Single		
Married	0.502 [†]	1.652
Divorced	-0.101 ^{NS}	0.904
Widow	0.040 ^{NS}	1.041
Property status Reference: Private school		
Public school	-0.124 ^{NS}	0.883
Areas Reference: Peri urbane/rural areas		
Urbane areas	0.012 ^{NS}	1.012

Based to the above results can be asserted:

Gender

Logistic regression analysis confirms the fact that the level of work motivation among teachers in lower secondary schools does not change based on gender, also. The possibility that female teachers have the same level of motivation at work to that of men is statistically equal. This is a conclusion similar to that communicated by Ahmad, S., Muneer, Rizwana, M. (2012); Gupta, M., Manju. G.

(2013); Mhammad. E, Al-Salameh, J. (2014); Bambang Budi Wiyono, (2016); Sultana A., Sarker, N.I., Prodhan, Sh. (2,017); Kumar, M. S., Balasubraman, P., (2019), while differing from the conclusion communicated by Mustafa M. Nur, Othman, N., (2012), according to which "Female teachers had higher work motivation..."

Age

Age is identified as a factor with statistically significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on work motivation among Albanian teachers in lower secondary school. The difference in the level of work motivation between young teachers (20-30 year old) and teachers that are > 30 years old are statistically significantly ($p < .05$), while between teachers aged 31-40 years old and > 40 years old, the difference is not significant ($p > 0.05$). The chances for teachers 31-40 year old to be motivated is estimated to be about 1.62 times higher than for teachers 20-30 years old. For teachers > 40 years old the chances of being motivated at work they are about 1.98 times greater than among their colleagues 20-30 years old.

The same type of relationship between the teacher's age with his work motivation has been communicated by other authors (Urošević, S., Milijić., 2012; Mark, A., 2015; while this conclusion is different from that published by Can, S. (2015), according to which, younger teachers are more affected by factors motivating teachers. The result that differs from the above is also communicated by Bambang Budi Wiyono (2016) according to which "...can be concluded that there was no differences in work motivation of teachers by gender, age, education level, work duration, rank, and school level".

Seniority

The results given in Table no.5,7 confirm the relationship between teaching experience and work motivation ($p < 0.05$). As the years at work increase, so do the opportunities for teachers to be more motivated to work. It is important to note that, the impact of seniority on teacher work motivation appears in teachers who have > 10 years working as teachers. Teachers who have > 10 years working as educators, the chances of being motivated at work they are about 2.85 times greater than among their colleagues who have not more than 5 years of working in lower secondary schools. This is a result that differs from the one communicated by Mustafa M. Nur, Othman, N., (2012), according to which "...teachers who had 4-to-9 years working experience had higher work motivation.."

Civil status

Civil status is identified as a factor with a statistically significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on work motivation among teacher (Table 6). Meanwhile, it

is important to note that the significant difference in the level of work motivation is identified when comparing single teachers with teachers that are married ($p < 0.05$), only According to data show in Table 7 married teachers, are 1.65 times more chance to be motivated at work compared to their single colleagues. Contrary to this result, Can, S. (2015) has communicated that: “..there is no significant correlation between factors motivating teachers and their marital status”.

Property status and areas where the school is located

The study does not support the hypothesis about the relationship between property status of the school, its location and the level of work motivation among the teachers. This is a result similar to that communicated by Kumar, A. (2017): “No significance difference exists in work motivation among government and private secondary school teachers”

The private education system in Albania is relatively new. Initiatives for the opening of private schools, as a rule, have not been driven by society's efforts to provide an educational service as effective as possible. At the core of these initiatives has been the economic interest of investors. Consequently, in private schools efforts are made, more than in public schools, to provide a quality and competitive service. This also means increased interest and care of investors and school managers having teachers as highly motivated at work. The above result according to which there is no significant difference in the level of work motivation among teachers in public and private schools, is not in line with the above reasoning.

Given the significant differences in social, economic, cultural and behavior of communities, between urban areas and peri-urban areas, the result found, according to which there is no significant difference in the level of work motivation between teachers in schools in the urban areas with them working in schools in periurban/rural areas, does not match the expectation.

Consequently, the need to conduct a more in-depth analysis of the relationship between the school's property status and location, on the one hand, and the motivation of teachers on the other, needs to be addressed.

Conclusions

Demographic factors affect in different ways the work motivation of teachers in lower secondary schools in Albania. There are no significant differences in the level of work motivation related to the

gender of the teacher. The age and seniority of teachers are factors that affect the work motivation among teachers. Teachers aged > 40 years and teachers who have > 10 years of work experience are more motivated at work. The civil status of the teacher affects the work motivation but this result is a consequence of the statistical difference in the levels of motivation at work between married teachers and others, only.

The study does not support the hypothesis about the relationship between property status of the school, its location and the level of work motivation among the teachers.

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